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Evaluation Study on The Impact of MRBOC Programs in Partner Community, Barangay San Isidro, Bais City, Negros Oriental

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(2024)

The Mother Rita Barcelo Outreach Center (MRBOC) is an extension and outreach office of La Consolacion College-Bais City whose goal is to craft a developmental and community-based program within the framework of Laudato Si the Encyclical Letter of Pope Francis. MRBOC has launched three (3) programs comprising five (5) projects in Barangay San Isidro Bais City, Negros Oriental, namely, mangrove planting, clean-up drives, feeding, livelihood, and scholarship programs.

Launched in 2019, the mission is to support and improve integrated coastal resource management and promote economically viable livelihood that would result in sustainable income generation for partner families, improved nutritional status of children, and access to basic education in the form of a scholarship program.

After five (5) years of implementation, MRBOC through its head, requested the director of LCC Research Office to form a team to conduct an impact evaluation of the programs implemented in Barangay San Isidro, Bais City. The study was done through (1) a review of relevant program documents; (2) conducting preliminary visits and meetings; (3) field surveys using a structured interview questionnaire, sociodemographic profile, and knowledge, attitude, and practice test, to use group discussion and key information management.

The respondents' demographic profile revealed the following: (1) majority female, married and catholic; (2) 36.67 percent were 60 years old and above, and about 23.33 percent attended tertiary education; (3) 43.33 work in the government and 66.67 percent do not own the land where they build their houses and 53.33 percent own a house.

The knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) test results were impressive. All of the respondents score 100% in knowledge, attitude, and practice about mangrove management.

In the planting of mangrove seedlings, the joint effort between local partners and volunteers planted a total of 20,000 seedlings in the area site. However, there was high mortality of the seedling growth based on the actual counting of seedling survival. Many factors were attributed to the high mortality of seedlings: (1) unhealthy seedlings due to stemborer and fungus infestation; (2) typhoon Odette which affected the growth and development of the seedlings; (3) lack of monitoring process of the seedlings.

The livelihood project was implemented by giving local partners start-up capital to open a small store for selling rice to members of the women's association. Initially, the association was able to earn ₱17,000.00 gross sale of its rice business. However, about ₱14,000.00 are still collectible from the members, leaving only a cash-on-hand of ₱3,000.00. This finding of low collection payment from members was due to low income, just enough to feed their family daily. Furthermore, offices need training in livelihood management.

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Another social intervention was the feeding program to nurture the nutritional status of poor children. Fifteen (15) feeding activities were implemented in the community targeting the malnourished children. Students, faculty, and personnel of LCC volunteered to serve the meals for children. More importantly, some parents of the student volunteers prepare the meals including cash to buy other materials. The parents of the children expressed that the program had a high impact in terms of the performance of their children in school and health improvement.

In terms of the scholarship program, to date, two (2) children with poor parents were made scholars for the school year 2024-2025. This intervention was found to be a good strategy for poor children to finish basic education to become professionals and to be part of the manpower pool of the community in the years to come.

Results in assessing the MRBOC management program and project indicated that program management meets its target objectives per project. Concerning institutionalization, the program has achieved high in (1) catalyzing support and facilitating resource mobilizing; (2) carrying activities aimed at strengthening the capacity and capability of partners and other stakeholders; (3) initiating the establishment of linkages at local, national, and international institutions. Overall, the above efforts got a high satisfaction rating at all levels of operation.

In conclusion, the Mother Rita Barcelo Outreach Center (MRBOC) has implemented innovative and integrated community-based programs in coastal management. It has improved the socio-economic conditions of the family partners through livelihood, feeding, and scholarship programs. Through a participatory and interactive approach to the project activities, family partners, particularly the women's association had been transformed to be a core of local volunteers in assisting project activities in the community.

MRBOC projects have made an impressive milestone in enhancing partners' knowledge, attitude, and practices in mangrove rehabilitation for biodiversity protection and ecological sound habitat for all living organisms. The result also made a partial improvement in the income generation of partners. Similarly, it has attracted support from other institutions and groups. The success of the program is due to the effectiveness and efficiency of the leadership of MRBOC in the operation of projects at different levels of partners. Moreover, the positive values like teamwork, honesty, solidarity, hard work, and love of God as manifested in the student's reflection paper are a good assurance for the continuity of the mangrove planting initiative in the area.

Some important general issues and recommendations, however, must be considered to improve the implementation of the program/projects such as (1) sustainability of project activities; (2) monitoring and evaluation scheme; (3) strengthening local management, leadership, and financial management; (4) networking and partnership; (5) local stewardship of programs/projects and technical training in mangrove management. Finally, specific issues should also be addressed such as (1) formal registration of the women's association and member education; (2) recruitment of more members; and (3) fund support from barangay and city government.

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